

THE IMPORTANCE OF IMPROVED SPEECH FORMATION IN PRIMARY TEACHERS

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Abstract: This article provides information on the importance of developing improved speech in primary school teachers and the concept of speech culture and its main elements.

Аннотация: В статье представлена информация о важности развития речевых навыков у учителей начальной школы, а также о понятии культуры речи и ее основных элементах.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarida takomillashgan nutqni shakllantirishning ahamiyati va nutq madaniyati haqida tushuncha va uning asosiy elementlari haqida ma'lumot beradi.

Keywords: speech, speech technique, speech culture, improved speech, types of speech, pedagogical technique, pedagogical skills of the teacher.

Ключевые слова: речь, техника речи, культура речи, совершенствование речи, типы речи, педагогическая техника, педагогическое мастерство учителя.

Kalit so'zlar: nutq, nutq texnikasi, nutq madaniyati, takomillashgan nutq, nutqning turlari, pedagogik texnika, o'qituvchining pedagogik mahorati.

A teacher plays a major role in the development and perfection of humanity. He is also important in the development of the individual. It is they who lead the nation to greatness, make a person mature and change the world for the better. As we, dear students, take our first steps towards school, we should never forget our first teacher, who found a place in the hearts of his students with his smiling faces from the schoolyard. First of all, we would like to thank our teacher who took a place in our hearts by holding a pen and a pencil in our hands and teaching us to write and read for the first time, and who introduced us to words such as Motherland, Mother, Father. However, it is worth emphasizing that teaching, like any other field, is an honorable and difficult profession. Theoretical knowledge, professional skills and qualifications, as well as professional competence, social and moral activity, maturity, and professional exemplary character are important in the image of future primary school teachers. Their ability to set themselves pedagogical tasks, effectively organize educational work, have an individual

approach to working with each student, and master the skills of working with educational materials are the basis for the effective organization of the educational process.

One of the main criteria for assessing the skills of a teacher is his speech. If we define speech in relation to the pedagogical process, speech is a thought that has become reality using the means of expression available in the language and is manifested in two forms:

- 1) internal speech;
- 2) external speech.

Internal speech is the thought, reasoning, and thinking of a person without opening his mouth, which is formed in the teacher's mind and consists of elements of language that have not yet been realized.

Speech, which occurs as real sounds through the influence and movement of the teacher's thoughts and ideas on the speech organs through language, is external speech, and it is a social phenomenon.

The teacher's speech activity consists of: speaking, reading, and listening. A speech event can be in the form of a monologue, dialogue, polylogue, declamation, as well as some texts and books. Speech is referred to the speaker in a specially designated manner by its volume.

Based on the analysis of pedagogical and psychological literature, the following characteristics of speech can be distinguished:

1. Functions: communication, influencing the individual, teaching and learning.
2. Forms: external speech (oral): monologue, dialogue, polylogue; writing: report, abstract, annotation, etc.; internal point.
3. Speech technique: professional quality of the teacher's voice: timbre, intonation, diction, tempo (120 words per minute).
4. Types of speech activity: reading, writing, speaking.
5. Speech styles: scientific, formal, colloquial, artistic, popular.
6. Requirements for speech: clarity of pronunciation, expressiveness, emotionality, intelligibility of diction, clear pronunciation of sounds, figurativeness, speech culture, compliance with the rules of word use, compliance with tempo.
7. Defects in speech: monotony, excess of tempo, incorrect diction, inappropriate use of words, violation of language rules.

The effectiveness of a teacher's speech is considered one of the main qualities of speech, and the accuracy and precision, logic, and clarity of speech are aimed at influencing the listener.

The effectiveness of a speech mainly refers to the teacher's oral speech process and the mental state that arises when it is received by students. That is, the orator-teacher must take into account the students, monitor their level of knowledge, even their age characteristics, their mood at the time of the speech, and monitor how their speech is received by students. It is not appropriate for teachers with professional knowledge to speak in a simple, straightforward language, and young teachers who do not have sufficient oratory education should not try to speak in a scientific and formal language. Thus, the orator-teacher is required to act according to the situation and is tasked with trying to fully convey to students any idea he wants to express.

Speaking in a language that students can understand and being able to convince them is one of the main conditions set before the teacher. For this, in addition to knowing the topic well, as mentioned above, the teacher must have a clearly defined plan for presenting it. It is necessary to start the speech by organizing the ideas in the speech in a primary and secondary way, connecting them, and first familiarizing the students with the speech plan. Taking into account time is one of the qualities of oratory. Because if the time for the speech is announced in advance and adhered to, and if possible, it is finished a little earlier, the students will not get bored. The talk about the effectiveness and expressiveness of the speech is, in a certain sense, a conclusion to the talk about the qualities of speech. Because showing the qualities of a good speech, analyzing some typical mistakes in speech, ultimately serves to form an effective speech. There are various ways and means to convey the ideas of a speech to the students in a meaningful way. They can also be called auxiliary means. For example, let's take humor or a story. A continuous stream of popular scientific ideas in a speech, its presentation in a monotonous manner, can bore both the student and any listener. At such times, it is very useful for the teacher to talk about humor, stories, and interesting events. It is even better if the humor is presented in a way that is appropriate to the content of the speech. This way, the student will both relax and become interested in the topic being studied.

It is also appropriate to present some thoughts and opinions within the scope of the topic in the speech. Such thoughts are used to prove the correctness and validity of the speaker's opinion, but their use should not be abused. The appropriate use of literary examples, wise sayings, and figurative language in the speech also ensures the achievement of positive results.

The teacher's behavior, gestures, and even clothing play a role in how a speech affects and impresses students. Qualities such as sincerity, politeness,

decency, and respect for students make students listen to the speech with attention.

Mastering the art of perfect oratory is a complex process that requires a lot of work for teachers. The sharpness, brightness, and originality of the speech are necessary to arouse emotions and interest in the listener and students, to attract their attention, and to convey the content of what is being said well.

Therefore, speech should be clear and fluent, grammatically correct, obey the rules of literary pronunciation, and be presented consistently from beginning to end. The knowledge learned through such speech will remain in the student's memory for a long time. Such speech meets the requirements of cultural speech. This requires constant research and self-improvement, philological knowledge, and constant speech practice from teachers.

Today's primary school teacher's improved speech is a guarantee of thorough mastery of educational materials by students. After all, primary school students pay special attention to the teacher's speech. The incorrect pronunciation of a letter or sound causes laughter. Speech in the same tone quickly tires students. Some experts say that the voice and its timbre are innate, but modern experimental physiology confirms that the quality of sound can change. Working on the expressiveness and purity of speech affects the fluency of thoughts. Speech occurs along with gestures, facial expressions, and movements, and continuous self-control allows you to successfully make adjustments to the choice of effective means.

Today, several sets of exercises on speech techniques have been developed. They are mainly based on the experience of teachers and improve the skills of breathing, sound formation and meaningful expression during speech, which allows the teacher to fully convey the meaning of his speech to students.

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